

INTEGRATED LEARNING TECHNOLOGY

M.K. Xashimova

Professor of the Tashkent University of Applied Sciences, Department of Pedagogy

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Abstract. *The article examines the issue of integration learning technology and its features, and integrated learning technology is a deep interpenetration, merging, as far as possible, generalized knowledge in a particular field in one educational material, examines the problems of integration in pedagogy in various aspects by studying the works of many researchers, analyzes the reasons for the emergence of such an approach, principles and features of integrated learning. The tasks implemented during the integrated lesson are described, the methodology of organizing the integrated lesson is presented, and the issue of the need to introduce an integration approach into educational practice is also analyzed.*

Keywords: *integration, educational activity, educational problems, teaching methods, functions, result, inter-subject relationship, combination, integrated approach, activity-based approach, problem-based approach, integration process, integration principle, integrative processes, integrative approach.*

Introduction. At the present stage, there is such a trend in the development of education as its technologization. This trend is to substantiate the technological approach as one of the leading conceptual foundations for the implementation of educational activities. The essence of the technological approach in a broad sense is the introduction of pedagogical technologies into the educational process in order to more effectively achieve the actual goals of education, upbringing and personal development.

Among a number of objective reasons that led to research in the field of technological approach to learning, it is necessary to single out the social need for a new quality of education at the turn of the 21st century, the psychological and pedagogical need for a purposeful influence on the formation and development of personality, the methodological need to choose the most effective teaching methods in their system. The new quality of education should reflect new processes of informatization of science and production, new means of communication, requires new ways of thinking, its algorithmization, as well as the effectiveness of the educational process.

Modern learning technologies are based on developing models of activity. Ways and directions of optimization of innovative pedagogical technologies are aimed at forming a highly competent personality, a competitive specialist capable of active and productive life in the context of globalization and industrialization of society.

Today, we are mainly talking about the creation, study and implementation of innovative pedagogical technologies in the educational process of educational organizations, the number of which is constantly growing with the development of pedagogical science and practice.

Integrated learning technology is a deep interpenetration, merging, as far as possible, generalized knowledge in a particular field in one educational material.

According to the classification of trends in the development of educational technologies, the integrated lesson belongs to the group of technologies of "education in the process of life",

which is a desire to move away from the school approach to education, extreme differentiation of subject learning and bring it into a natural organic connection with life.

The subject-based classroom-based learning system is based on the presentation of the content of education in the form of academic subjects based on sciences that differentially study the world. This division of knowledge into scientific fields arose due to man's inability to know the whole world in all its connections and relationships. Subject differentiation facilitates the process of cognition, but affects its quality. Students have a fang-like idea of the world and its laws, in which not everything is connected and dependent, and much exists by itself. Such non-systemic knowledge spoils thinking and distorts attitudes towards the world and oneself. Thus, there is a need at the level of education to combine the knowledge of different sciences about the same objects of reality, i.e. the need for inter-subject relations of academic disciplines.

The integrated lesson is one of the innovations of modern education. This technology intrudes into the educational process and connects seemingly incompatible subjects. It is permeated with inter-subject connections and offers students knowledge of many fields of science, art, culture, as well as real everyday life. The concept of integrated learning includes not only a tolerant attitude, but also the use of modern technologies in education. After all, the transition to this type of progressive education requires modernizing the entire school system. Exactly:

- attract the necessary specialists who will help teachers during teaching;
- use innovative pedagogical solutions and ideas;
- adapt the curriculum to meet the needs of all children in an integrated classroom;
- focus on the development of creative and cognitive abilities;
- actively involve parents in the educational process.

By integration in the pedagogical process, researchers understand one of the aspects of the development process associated with the unification of previously disparate parts into a whole. This process can take place both within the framework of an already established system and within the framework of a new system. The essence of the integration process is qualitative transformations within each element included in the system. The problems of integration in pedagogy are considered in different aspects in the works of many researchers. The works of V. V. Kraevsky, A.V. Petrovsky, N. F. Talyzina consider the issues of integration of pedagogy with other sciences. G. D. Glazer and V. S. Lednev reveal the ways of integration in the content of education. The works of L. I. Novikova and V. A. Karakovsky reveal the problems of integrating educational influences on students. Integration in the organization of education is considered in the works of S. M. Gapeenkov and G. F. Fedorets.

Results and discussion

Based on the highlighted methodological provisions, scientists identify a number of concepts: the integration process, the principle of integration, integrative processes, integrative approach. The principle of integration presupposes the interconnection of all components of the learning process, all elements of the system, and the relationship between the systems. He is a leader in the development of goal-setting, defining the content of education, its forms and methods. Integrative processes are processes of qualitative transformation of individual elements of a system or the entire system. The need for integrated lessons is explained by a number of reasons:

1. The world around children is known to them in all its diversity and unity, and often the subjects of the school cycle, aimed at studying individual phenomena, divide it into disparate fragments.

2. Integrated lessons develop the potential of students themselves, encourage them to actively explore the surrounding reality, to comprehend and find cause-and-effect relationships, to develop logic, thinking, and communication skills.

3. The form of integrated lessons is unusual and interesting. The use of various types of work during the lesson keeps students' attention at a high level, which allows us to talk about the sufficient effectiveness of lessons. Integrated lessons open up significant pedagogical possibilities.

4. Integration in modern society explains the need for integration in education. Modern society needs highly qualified, well-trained specialists. Integration provides an opportunity for self-realization, self-expression, creativity of teachers and students, and promotes the development of abilities.

Principles, forms and advantages of integrated learning. An integrative approach means the implementation of the principle of integration in any component of the pedagogical process, ensures the integrity and consistency of the pedagogical process. Integrated learning has its own principles and features:

- develops the individual characteristics of each child;
- creates conditions for close cooperation between schools, teachers, specialized specialists and parents;
- teaches a certain culture that helps children to respect children who are different from them and accept differences without offending others;
- creates a supportive space where each child feels valued and able to cope with all tasks.

When planning and organizing integrated classes, it is important for a teacher to consider the following conditions:

1. An integrated lesson combines knowledge blocks of two or three different subjects, so it is extremely important to correctly identify the main purpose of the integrated lesson. If a common goal is defined, then only the information that is necessary for its implementation is taken from the content of the subjects.

2. Integration helps to relieve tension, overload, and fatigue of students by switching them to a variety of activities during the lesson. When planning, careful determination of the optimal load of various types of student activities in the lesson is required.

3. When conducting an integrated lesson by teachers (leading different subjects), careful coordination of actions is required. In the form of integrated lessons, it is advisable to conduct generalizing lessons that will reveal the problems most important for two or more subjects, but any lesson with its own structure can be an integrated lesson if it involves knowledge, skills and the results of analysis of the studied material using methods of other sciences and other academic subjects. In an integrated lesson of several subjects, one is the leader.

Advantages of integrated lessons:

- contribute to increasing the motivation of learning, the formation of cognitive interest of students, a holistic scientific picture of the world and consideration of the phenomenon from several sides;
- to a greater extent than regular lessons, they contribute to the development of speech, the formation of students' ability to compare, generalize, and draw conclusions;
- they not only deepen the understanding of the subject, broaden the horizons, but also contribute to the formation of a well-rounded, harmoniously and intellectually developed personality;

• Integration is a source of finding new connections between facts that confirm or deepen certain conclusions;

• integration provides an opportunity for self-realization, self-expression, creativity of the teacher, promotes the disclosure of the abilities of his students. Integration is a source of finding new facts that confirm or deepen certain conclusions and observations of students in various subjects.

1. Diagram. An integrated lesson.

An integrated lesson is a special type of lesson that combines teaching in several disciplines simultaneously while studying a single concept, topic, or phenomenon. In such a lesson, there are always two main disciplines: the leading discipline, which acts as an integrator, and auxiliary disciplines, which contribute to the deepening, expansion, and refinement of the material of the leading discipline.

Tasks implemented during the integrated lesson

The integrated lesson allows you to solve a number of tasks that are difficult to implement within the framework of traditional approaches:

- increasing the motivation of learning activities due to the non-standard form of the lesson (this is unusual, so it's interesting);
- consideration of concepts that are used in different subject areas;
- organization of purposeful work with mental operations: comparison, generalization, classification, analysis, synthesis, etc;
- showing inter-subject relationships and their application in solving various tasks;
- organically link the material together;
- conduct the lesson without overloading the children.

Integrated lesson methodology

Teachers rarely resort to using an integrated lesson. Before deciding on an integrated lesson, it is necessary to turn the teacher into an ally (there may be more teachers, depending on which subjects will be integrated) of another subject with which integration is underway. Both teachers will have to identify a common interest in integrating their disciplines. Both teachers

should be aware that they will have a lot of work and a lot of time and effort, much more than when preparing and conducting separate lessons.

The bottleneck of an integrated lesson is the technology of interaction between two teachers, the sequence and order of their actions, the content and methods of presenting the material, and the duration of each action. Their interaction can be built in different ways. It can be equal, with equal participation of each of them; one of them can act as a moderator, and the other as an assistant or consultant; one teacher can lead the entire lesson in the presence of another as an active observer and guest.

The duration of the integrated lesson can also be different. But most often they use two or three scheduled hours combined into one lesson. Any integrated lesson is associated with going beyond the narrow scope of a single subject, the corresponding conceptual and terminological system and method of cognition. It is possible to overcome the superficial and formal study of the issue, expand information, change the aspect of the study, deepen understanding, clarify concepts and laws, summarize the material, combine the experience of students and the theory of its understanding, systematize the studied material.

Integrated lessons can combine a wide variety of disciplines in their entirety, giving rise to integrative subjects such as Fundamentals of Life Safety or World Art Culture, as well as any components of the pedagogical process: goals, principles, content, methods and means of teaching. When, for example, content is taken, any of its components can be distinguished for integration in it: concepts, laws, principles, definitions, signs, phenomena, hypotheses, events, facts, ideas, and problems. It is also possible to integrate content components such as intellectual and practical skills and abilities. These components from different disciplines, combined in one lesson, become system forming, and educational material is assembled around them and brought into a new system. The system-forming factor is the main one in the organization of the lesson, since the methodology and technology of its construction developed further will be determined by it.

The process of preparing and conducting an integrated lesson has its own specifics. It consists of several stages:

1. Preparatory (planning, organization of a creative group, designing the lesson content, rehearsal).

2. Executive. The lesson itself.

The purpose of the first stage is to arouse students' interest in the topic of the lesson and its content. There may be various ways to arouse interest, for example, by describing a problematic situation or an interesting case. In the final part of the lesson, it is necessary to summarize everything said in the lesson, summarize the students' reasoning, and formulate clear conclusions.

3. Reflexive. At this stage, the lesson is analyzed. It is necessary to take into account all its advantages and disadvantages.

In the course of preparatory activities, the teacher determines:

- their motives for conducting an integrated lesson and its purpose;
- the composition of integration, a set of combined components;
- Leading backbone and auxiliary components;
- the form of integration;
- the nature of the connections between the joined material;
- the structure (sequence) of the material arrangement;
- methods and techniques of its presentation;
- methods and techniques of students' processing of new material;

- ways to increase the visibility of educational material;
- distribution of roles with teachers of the integrated subject;
- criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of the lesson;
- the form of recording the prepared lesson;
- Forms and types of student exposure control in this lesson.

The definition of the form of integration depends on the purpose of the lesson and the choice of the system-forming component, on what the integration will be conducted around. There are different forms:

- subject – figurative, used in recreating a broader and holistic view of the subject of cognition;
- conceptual, when a phenomenological analysis of the phenomenon that makes up this concept is carried out, and the conceptual field of the concept is developed;
- ideological, when a spiritual and moral justification of a phenomenon studied by science is made, or spiritual and moral postulates are proved by scientific facts;
- active, in which a procedure is performed for generalizing the methods of activity, transferring and applying them in new conditions;
- conceptual, in which students practice developing new ideas, suggestions, and ways to solve a learning problem.

Conclusions

Of course, the choice of one of the forms of integration is significantly influenced by the teacher's knowledge of the very phenomenon of pedagogical integration, its types, forms, structures and technology of implementation. The level of students' development and their ability to combine knowledge from different disciplines also have an impact. In this case, we also need practical experience of participating in lessons of this kind. Each subsequent integrated lesson will be easier for all participants in the pedagogical process.

After we have determined the purpose of the lesson, the integrated blocks of knowledge, identified one of them as a system-forming one, and finally decided on the form of integration, we should do a very delicate job - considering the connections that should be established between the integrated blocks of knowledge. Connections are established or restored sequential dependencies of integrated components among themselves. At this stage, the teacher will stay a little longer: it is not so easy to find connections and dependencies, to determine their nature. There is no choice here, but there are tasks determined by the nature and nature of the phenomena being studied.

The connections between the integrated components can be very different. The following are most common in school practice:

- Links of origin;
- Generation connections;
- Connections of construction (in case of systematization and generalization of knowledge);
- Management communications.

Links of origin are established where cause and effect relationships are identified between components. As you can see, we are not talking about a simple combination of knowledge from different academic disciplines, but only those that reveal the origins, causes or conditions of origin of the subject of knowledge studied in the leading lesson. Knowledge introduced from another

discipline performs an explanatory function. With these connections, the student learns to identify the dependencies of events, facts, and phenomena.

The relations of generation are very similar to the relations of origin, but they have the specificity that they place the system-forming subject under study in the position of the cause generating the effects studied in another academic subject. So, if a chemistry teacher conducts an integrated lesson on poisons, then he draws on material from biology. Relatively speaking, its material serves as the basis for the appearance of biological consequences, the consideration of which is not included in the knowledge of chemistry. Integrated lessons with such connections teach students to go beyond the scope of the subject and see the consequences of their narrow, locally committed actions, the impact of discoveries on people's lives and the development of science and industry.

The connections between integrated knowledge are created by the teacher where the combined components act as equals, interacting with each other in a situation set by the main subject. Let's imagine lessons on the use of computer science in learning the Russian language, lessons on the topics of "Pushkin in music", "Yesenin's landscape lyrics in the works of artists", "Physics and Poetry", etc. Here, each integrated component plays the role of a new form of presentation of the phenomenon under study: poetry in painting, physics in music. In such lessons, students learn to discover analogies, transfer knowledge from one iconic form to another.

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